

5. Даций Н.В. Взаємовідносини органів публічної влади та інститутів громадянського суспільства / Н. В. Даций // Збірник наукових праць ДонДУУ : Сучасні тенденції державного управління в умовах соціально-економічного розвитку» : Серія «Державне управління». – Т.ХV, Вип. 286, 2014. – С. 37–51.

6. Філіпчук В. О. Європейська інтеграція як засіб державотворення в Україні : автореф. дис. ... канд. наук з держ. упр. : 25.00.01 / Філіпчук В. О. ; Нац. акад. держ. упр. при Президентові України. – К., 2014. – 22 с.

References

1. Martynenko, V.M. "Demokratyzatsiia mekhanizmiv derzhavnoho upravlinnia protsesamy suspilnykh transformatsii." Abstract Diss. ... PhD in Public Administration. Kharkiv, (2005): 38. Print.

2. Ploskyi, K.V. "Molodizhnyi hromadskyi rukh yak chynnyk derzhavotvorennia v Ukraini." Abstract Diss. ... PhD in Public Administration. Kyiv, (2009): 20. Print.

3. Semenov, V.M. "Rehionalni osoblyvosti derzhavotvorennia v Ukraini." Abstract Diss. ... PhD in Public Administration. Kharkiv, (2009): 16. Print.

4. Ukraine. President of Urraine. *Stratehiia staloho rozvytku «Ukraina - 2020»*. Available to: www.president.gov.ua/documents/18688.html. Accessed: 08 Feb. 2017.

5. Datsii, N.V. "Relations between public authorities and civil society institutions." *Contemporary trends in public administration in the conditions of socio-economic development. Series "Public administration"* 286 (XV) (2014): 37-51. Print.

6. Filipchuk, V.O. "Yevropeiska intehratsiia yak zasib derzhavotvorennia v Ukraini." Abstract Diss. ... PhD in Public Administration. Kyiv, (2014): 22. Print.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1247866

УДК 351.88:339.96

Myrna N., Ph.D in Public Administration, associated professor, department of law and european integration, Kharkiv Regional Institute of Public Administration, National Academy of Public Administration under the Office of the President of Ukraine, Kharkiv,

Padafet I., Ph.D in Public Administration, associated professor, Department of Personal Management Department, Kharkiv Regional Institute of Public Administration, Kharkiv

UKRAINE'S ASSOCIATION AGENDA AND PECULARITIES OF ACQUISITION OF THE INTERNATIONAL TECHNICAL ASSISTANCE

The unstable political, legislative and administrative context in Ukraine limited the effectiveness of EU assistance. EU–Ukraine cooperation advanced in the wake of the 2014 Maidan events, but the challenges faced by Ukraine still heavily affect the re-

form process. The EU prompt and emergency response to the Ukraine crisis of 2014 shown EU capability to allocate and disburse large amounts of money rapidly and without a predefined strategy. Ukraine's reporting mechanism and scientific and methodological support are examined.

Keywords: *Association Agenda, budget support, grants, Paris Declaration, technical assistance.*

Problem setting. According to the OECD, Ukraine ranked 45th among the top-50 recipients of international assistance [5, p. 15]. In 2016, Syria, Ethiopia and Afghanistan were the top-3 recipients of international assistance. Together, they received more than \$16 bn. However, Ukraine ranks second among the developing countries in Europe, beaten only by Turkey. Ukraine received \$1,7 bn in 2016, which accounts for 16% of all the assistance the region received that year [6, p. 2]. This is twice as much as what the country received in 2013.

The international technical assistance is a tool of the economic development. It is also used to support interests of a country at external markets. Since 1992 in Ukraine there have been introduced and implemented projects with an overall budget of approximately \$ 10 milliard spent by different donors. In fact a state budget of Ukraine annually receives about UAH 2,5 billion which is 1 % of a total budget revenues. The biggest donors of Ukraine are the USA and the European Union.

Paper objective. Main goal is to examine a reporting mechanism that would enable Ukraine, as a recipient of donor funds, to provide a comprehensive review of how the total volume of international assistance was utilized.

Paper main body. EU–Ukraine cooperation is part of the European Neighbourhood Policy and its eastern dimension, the Eastern Partnership. Cooperation progressed mainly with the signing of the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement (PCA) in 1994, the EU–Ukraine Action Plan in 2005 and the Association Agenda in 2009, which was updated in 2011, 2013 and 2015.

EU and Ukraine signed the political provisions of the Association Agreement on 21 March 2014 and the remaining provisions on 27 June 2014. The Agreement provides for the enhancement of EU–Ukraine relations in all areas of cooperation and also constitutes a reform agenda, based on a comprehensive programme to bring Ukrainian legislation into line with EU norms.

Financial assistance, in the form of grants to help Ukraine implement the Action Plan, was provided mainly by means of the European Neighbourhood and Partnership Instrument (ENPI), which was replaced by the European Neighbourhood Instrument (ENI) in 2014. ENPI bilateral assistance to Ukraine was programmed via the 2007-2013 Country Strategy Paper (CSP) and two national indicative programmes (2007-2010 and 2011-2013 NIPs). No new CSP or NIP has been announced since then due to the difficult situation. Most ENPI–ENI assistance (65 %) was granted using a sector budget support approach. Ukraine also received EU grants through the Instrument for Nuclear Safety Cooperation and the Instrument contributing to Stability and Peace.

In parallel to the significant increase in EU assistance to Ukraine in 2014, the EU established new entities calling upon additional expertise to advise Ukraine on the reform process. The two most notable initiatives are the Support Group for Ukraine (SGUA) from the Commission and the EU Advisory Mission for Civilian Security Sector Reform (EUAM) [7, p. 9]. Both the SGUA and the EUAM significantly enhance EU–Ukraine cooperation. They provide expertise in targeted sectors already being assisted by the EU Delegation.

Projects of the international technical assistance vary in financing and the activity itself. They can include consultations, expert assessments, exchanges and study programs in different fields of economy and an unstinting support to governmental measures to implement large projects with essential technical components.

At different times the Ukrainian governors paid different attention to the attraction of assistance and the control for its effective use. However since 2007 this field has been extremely active. First of all the external changes in the assistance played a great part when Ukraine within the frames of the European Neighborhood and Partnership Instrument gained a unique opportunity to use a budget support of about € 1 billion. The financial and economic crisis also made a great impact on the external financing provided to Ukraine.

Some of the oligarchs took their own initiatives for proposing reforms for Ukraine and establish a restoration fund. But those activities largely duplicate those of the Ukrainian government and the EU.

Thus despite the small amount of external assistance lately there has been a high interest to the international technical assistance (ITA) which can be proven by the intensive regulation appearing on this issue.

The 2007 was a remarkable year for Ukraine as the country joined the Paris Declaration on Aid Effectiveness and entered a new level of disbursement. The Paris Declaration is a practical scheme used to monitor a partnership progress with a general purpose to improve the quality of assistance and enhance its influence on the development. Ukraine's joining the Paris Declaration was to encourage an effective organizational and legal coordination between donors and international financial institutions (IFI) and the contractual base, to improve an efficient provision of assistance as well as to introduce IFI and ITA finances with due regards to the needs of Ukraine. These needs were determined in the strategic trends and tasks to introduce the international technical assistance and cooperate with international financial institutions for 2009-2012, approved by the regulation of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine dd. September 3, 2009 No. 1156.

The strategic trends are as follows [2]:

1. To improve the competitiveness of the national economy on the investment and innovative basis.
2. To enhance social living standards, citizens' health, to ensure humanitarian development, civil society development and the rule of law.
3. To eliminate structural restrictions.

4. To encourage Ukraine's European and Euro-Atlantic integration.
5. To enhance ecological, nuclear and radioactive protection as well as state and citizens' security.

However the strategic frames of attracting the ITA and cooperating with IFIs can only solve a problem in part. The characteristic features of a budget support are the eligibility conditions that should be fulfilled before the donor makes a payment.

Despite the fact that Ukraine had only partially satisfied these conditions in December 2009 the EU provided first € 23 billion of the first tranche (€ 82 billion) to support the implementation of the Energy Strategy of Ukraine. Only two years later the Regulation of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine dd. September 15, 2010 No. 841 defined the procedure to monitor programs of the EU budget support to Ukraine [1].

To meet the conditions of the Paris Declaration it is necessary to apply such a coordination of the international technical assistance which corresponds to the strategic development of the state in whole and regions in particular, determines clear strategic priorities for the international technical assistance and coordinates them with national ones, takes national systems of financial management into consideration, creates a structure of project analysis with regard to its implementation and accountability etc.

One of such documents is the directive of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine dd. October 20, 2011 No. 1075-p "On approval of the Concept of planning, attraction, an effective use and monitoring of the international technical assistance and cooperation with IFIs" [3].

However in October 2011 the European Commission developed a new Communication on the "Future approach to EU budget support to third countries" containing 5 provisions to address the following development challenges and objectives [4]:

- Promoting human rights and democratic values;
- Improving financial management, macroeconomic stability, inclusive growth and the fight against corruption and fraud;
- Promoting sector reforms and improving sector service delivery;
- State-building in fragile states and addressing development challenges of SIDS and OCTs;
- Improving domestic revenue mobilization and reducing dependency on aid.

The European Commission is now providing the budget support only to those countries that can meet the eligibility conditions appearing in different legal frameworks [4]:

- National/sector policies and reforms;
- Stable macro-economic framework;
- Public financial management;
- Transparency and oversight of the budget.

The public availability of budgetary information is essential for promoting greater scrutiny of the budget.

Conclusions of the research. The situation at present emphasizes on the following needs:

- to revise the strategic priorities of the international technical assistance and cooperation with international financial institutes for 2021-2027 i.e. a period of a new EU budget;

- to establish an effective coordination of the international technical assistance in European integration and correlate it with the European neighborhood policy, foreign technical assistance, state budget and socio-economic development of Ukraine;

- performing an audit of the structure of the total volume of international assistance and various types of aid projects, and their connection to the country's reform priorities set up by policy makers.

Another important task is a scientific and methodological support to ITA policy and cooperation with IFIs that should cover the following issues:

- to provide a scientific and methodological support to ministers, local governments and their officials;

- to adjust national and regional systems of training, retraining and in-service training for ITA project employees;

- creating an expert/think tank network to provide aid effectiveness analysis ;

- to develop methodology of the Paris Declaration implementation and compliance.

It is only possible to formulate and implement the strategic trends of ITA's attraction if the efforts in scientific, technical, financial, administrative and managerial fields are consolidated; all the available scientific, technical and innovative potential of donors and Ukrainian experts is applied; all the international informational resources are used.

References

1. Regulation of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine dd. September 15, 2010 No. 841. *On procedure to prepare, implementation and monitor programs of the EU sector budget support to Ukraine.* Available to: <http://zakon.rada.gov.ua/cgi-bin/laws/main.cgi?nreg=841-2010-%EF>. Accessed: 05 May. 2018.

2. Regulation of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine dd. September 3, 2009 No. 1156. *The strategic trends and tasks to introduce the international technical assistance and cooperate with international financial institutions for 2009-2012.* Available to: <http://zakon.rada.gov.ua/cgi-bin/laws/main.cgi?nreg=1156-2009-%F0>. Accessed: 05 May. 2018.

3. Directive of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine dd. October 20, 2011 No. 1075-p. *On approval of the Concept of planning, attraction, an effective use and monitoring of the international technical assistance and cooperation with international fi-*

nancial institutions. Available to: <http://zakon2.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/1075-2011-%D1%80>. Accessed: 05 May. 2018.

4. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. *The future approach to EU budget support to third countries» 13.10.2011 COM(2011) 638*. Available to: http://ec.europa.eu/europeaid/how/delivering-aid/budget-support/documents/future_eu_budget_support_en.pdf. Accessed: 05 May. 2018.

5. OECD report. *Development aid at a glance statistics by region, Developing countries*. Available to: <https://www.oecd.org/dac/stats/documentupload/World-Development-Aid-at-a-Glance.pdf>. Accessed: 05 May. 2018.

6. OECD report. *Development aid at a glance statistics by region, Developing countries*. Available to: <http://www.oecd.org/dac/financing-sustainable-development/development-finance-data/World-Development-Aid-at-a-Glance-2018.pdf>. Accessed: 05 May. 2018.

7. Special report European Court of Auditors. *EU assistance to Ukraine*. Available to: https://www.eca.europa.eu/Lists/ECADocuments/SR16_32/SR_UKRAINE_EN.pdf. Accessed: 05 May. 2018.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1240892
УДК 316.77:351(045)

*Польська Т. Д., к.філософ. н., доц., НТУ України
«КПІ ім. Ігоря Сікорського», м. Київ*

*Polska T., Ph.D of Philosophy, Associate Professor, Associate Professor of the
Dept. of the Theory and Practice Administration, National Technical University
of Ukraine, Kyiv*

ВІДНОСИНИ З ГРОМАДСКІСТЮ: СОЦІАЛЬНО ВІДПОВІДАЛЬНА КОМУНІКАЦІЯ В ПУБЛІЧНОМУ УПРАВЛІННІ

PUBLIC RELATION: SOCIAL RESPONSIBLE COMMUNICATION IN PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION

Стаття представляє соціокультурний підхід до відносин з громадськістю як спосіб аналізу зростаючого значення відносин з громадськістю в їх соціальному, культурному та політичному контекстах. Представлена концепція зв'язків з громадськістю як не просто організаційного інструменту, а соціально відповіда-